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Data Review

Data Citation

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Abstract

This data review examines the Human Development Index (HDI), a composite indicator developed by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) to assess human development beyond economic growth through three dimensions: health, education, and standard of living. The HDI is calculated using life expectancy data from the UN Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA), education indicators from the UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS), and GNI per capita data from the World Bank and International Monetary Fund (IMF). Since 2010, the index has been based on a geometric mean to reduce the assumption of substitutability between dimensions. Despite its widespread use, scholars have criticised the HDI's fixed thresholds and limited scope, arguing that it overlooks factors such as empowerment and inequality. The review focuses on the HDI in general, and more specifically on data for 15 relevant countries covered by Discuss Data, including Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, the Russian Federation, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, and Uzbekistan. HDI data for these countries is available annually from 1990 or - for some counties later starting 1995, 2000 or 2005 - facilitating cross-national comparisons. However, for countries undergoing political or demographic transitions, such as Ukraine and Georgia, the HDI may obscure internal disparities and should be supplemented with more detailed indicators.

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Data Review – Human Development Index

The Human Development Index (HDI) is a widely used composite indicator developed and published annually by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) since 1990 (UNDP n.d.-b). It aims to measure key dimensions of human development in almost all countries beyond economic growth: health, education, and standard of living (UNDP n.d.-b).

The HDI “is the most well-known index of human development. It is based on the idea that human development means that people have long and healthy lives, are knowledgeable, and have a decent standard of living” (Herre et al. 2023). Thus, the index is calculated based on three core dimensions:

- 1) Health: measured through life expectancy at birth,
- 2) Education: a combination of mean years of schooling and expected years of schooling, and
- 3) Standard of living: Gross National Income (GNI) per capita (UNDP n.d.-b).

The HDI uses statistical and national administrative data for its indicators (UNDP 2015: 3). Specifically, the main data sources for the HDI are as follows: life expectancy is provided by United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA), educational statistics come from UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS) and Barro & Lee (2013), and GNI per capita is typically drawn from the World Bank, International Monetary Fund (IMF), or UN Statistical Division datasets (UNDP 2015: 3).

Since 2010, the HDI has been calculated using the geometric mean of the normalised indices for these three dimensions, replacing the previous arithmetic mean (Herrero et al. 2012: 248). The geometric mean is calculated by multiplying the three dimension indices (health, education, standard of living) and then taking the cube root (UNDP 2023/2024: 4):

$$\text{HDI} = (I_{\text{Health}} * I_{\text{Education}} * I_{\text{Income}})^{1/3}$$

This method differs from the arithmetic mean, in which the three values are simply averaged. The change to the geometric mean was introduced to prevent uneven development across dimensions and reduce the assumption of “perfect substitutability” (Herrero et al. 2012: 250). This approach also implies that a proportional change (e.g., a 1% decline) in any of the three indices has an equal effect on the HDI, thus reinforcing the normative idea that all three dimensions are equally important. As the UNDP (2015) explains, “a low achievement in one dimension is not anymore linearly compensated for by high achievement in another dimension” (UNDP 2015: 4), which leads to a more balanced and realistic assessment of human development across dimensions (UNDP 2015: 4).

The index values are normalised using fixed minimum and maximum values (UNDP n.d.-b: Table 1 – Human Development Index and components):

- Life expectancy: min. 20 years, capped at 85 years
- Expected schooling: capped at 18 years
- GNI per capita: min. \$100, capped at \$75,000

These bounds are supposed to ensure comparability across countries and reflect historically informed thresholds. For instance, the 20-year minimum for life expectancy is based on evidence that societies cannot sustainably reproduce below this level (UNDP 2015: 5).

The income cap at \$75,000 was introduced to prevent very high incomes from disproportionately influencing the HDI, recognising “income is instrumental to human development, but the contribution diminishes as incomes rise” (UNDP 2015: 5).

Methodological Changes

Over time, multiple methodological changes have been introduced to the HDI: In 2010, Gross Domestic Product (GDP) was replaced with GNI, and education indicators were updated to expected and mean years of schooling (Herrero et al. 2012: 249).

The switch from GDP to GNI reflects a conceptual adjustment: while GDP measures the value of all goods and services produced within a country (CSO n.d.), “GNI is the gross domestic product, plus net receipts from abroad of compensation of employees, property income and net taxes less subsidies on production” (OECD n.d.) – and thus “gives a more precise picture of the national economy” (CSO n.d.).

Additionally, GNI per capita in the HDI is expressed in “purchasing power parity (PPP) international dollars” (UNDP 2015: 3) to enable meaningful comparison between countries with different cost-of-living levels (UNDP 2015: 2, 3). Due to the periodic changes in methodology and revisions to PPP conversion rates – particularly those introduced in 2014 and 2015 – HDI values from different years are not necessarily directly comparable. The UNDP advises using “consistent data” provided in the latest reports for any time-series analysis to ensure consistency (UNDP 2015: 3).

Several researchers have critically examined the consequences of these adjustments. Among others, both Herrero et al. (2012) and Lind (2019) emphasise that normalisation limits are arbitrary and distort country rankings, “especially among the very highly developed countries” (Lind 2019: 411-412, 422, quote 412; Herrero et al. 2012: 254).

Alternatives

Several scholars have proposed modifications or extensions to the HDI: Lind (2019) developed an alternative “Index H”, which uses historical data to derive parameter values, eliminating arbitrary thresholds and enabling longitudinal analysis (Lind 2019: 410, 418). Some critics such as Ranis et al. (2006) argue that the HDI reflects only a limited range of human development and ignores essential dimensions such as empowerment or political freedom (Ranis et al. 2006: 331 Table 2). Their broader framework includes 11 categories of human development and demonstrates that many of these are only weakly correlated with HDI values (Ranis et al. 2006: 348).

Using the HDI

According to the UNDP (n.d.-b) “the HDI simplifies and captures only part of what human development entails. It does not reflect on inequalities, poverty, human security, empowerment, etc.” (UNDP n.d.-b). Despite these limitations, the HDI remains an adequate tool for cross-national analysis. However, it may be used in combination with other indicators – like the ones identified by Ranis et al. (2006) – to fully capture the broader concept of human development (UNDP n.d.-b).

Its wide coverage of countries and easy accessibility support comparative research and policy monitoring.

The HDI also serves as a basis for several composite indices, including:

- Gender Development Index (GDI),
- Gender Social Norms Index (GSNI),
- Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI),
- Inequality-Adjusted HDI (IHDI), and
- Planetary Pressure-adjusted HDI (PHDI) (UNDP n.d.-a).

The HDI is relevant for comparative analysis of social policy trajectories in – among others – post-socialist and developing countries. However, for countries experiencing political or demographic transitions (e.g., Ukraine and Georgia), it may mask important within-country inequalities or structural vulnerabilities. Researchers may use the HDI critically and supplement it with more detailed or multidimensional data where possible. All 15 countries relevant for Discuss Data are covered in the HDI dataset (see table 1), with values for all three dimensions – health, education, and standard of living – available. In most cases, complete annual data series from 1990 to 2022 (as of April 2025) are provided. For Azerbaijan (1995), Belarus (1995), Georgia (2000), Turkmenistan (2005), and Uzbekistan (2000), data coverage begins later (UNDP n.d.-b).

Table 1: Discuss Data Relevant Country Coverage (UNDP n.d.-b)

Country	Year	Values (of 3)	Data collection
Armenia	1990 - 2022	3	Annually
Azerbaijan	1995 - 2022	3	Annually
Belarus	1995 - 2022	3	Annually
Estonia	1990 - 2022	3	Annually
Georgia	2000 - 2022	3	Annually
Kazakhstan	1990 - 2022	3	Annually
Kyrgyzstan	1990 - 2022	3	Annually
Latvia	1990 - 2022	3	Annually
Lithuania	1990 - 2022	3	Annually
Republic of Moldova	1990 - 2022	3	Annually
Russian Federation	1990 - 2022	3	Annually
Tajikistan	1990 - 2022	3	Annually
Turkmenistan	2005 - 2022	3	Annually
Ukraine	1990 - 2022	3	Annually
Uzbekistan	2000 - 2022	3	Annually

Availability

HDI data from 1990 onward is publicly available via the [UNDP Human Development Data Center](#). The website provides: country-specific profiles, annual reports and methodological notes, JSON and Excel download options, as well as filter by indicator options. As of April 2025, no registration is required for access (UNDP n.d.-b).

The HDI dataset is published under the Creative Commons Attributions 3.0 IGO license, allowing the sharing and adaptation with appropriate attributions and credit (UNDP n.d.-c). Users must “provide a link to the license, and indicate where changes were made. Furthermore, they must note that HDI values are recalculated annually (UNDP n.d.-c).

The UNDP recommends adding the following text “particularly in print publications” (UNDP n.d.-c): “The entire series of Human Development Index (HDI) values and rankings are recalculated every year using the same the most recent (revised) data and functional forms. The HDI rankings and values in the 2014 Human Development Report cannot therefore be compared directly to indices published in previous Reports. Please see hdr.undp.org for more information.

The HDI was created to emphasize that people and their capabilities should be the ultimate criteria for assessing the development of a country, not economic growth alone. The HDI can also be used to question national policy choices, asking how two countries with the same level of GNI per capita can end up with different human development outcomes.” (UNDP n.d.-c)

Funding

The UNDP does not list a specific, singular funding source for the HDI. However, the UNDP itself is funded through voluntary contributions from United Nations members and does receive thematic and programmatic donations from governments, development banks, NGOs, and foundations (UNDP 2024: 11).

Note

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